

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Mapping service quality through demographic clustering in Northern Luzon State University

Romano P. Cammayo *

Isabela State University.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 24(03), 1609–1619

Publication history: Received on 10 October 2024; revised on 14 December 2024; accepted on 17 December 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.3.3847>

Abstract

This study evaluated the implementation and impact of the Citizen's Charter at Isabela State University, Echague Campus, with a focus on its effectiveness in improving service delivery among non-teaching and teaching personnel. Employing a quantitative research design, the study utilized a structured survey to assess various dimensions of the Citizen's Charter, including tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, quality assurance, and empathy. A total of 139 participants, comprising non-teaching and teaching personnel, provided their insights and satisfaction ratings. The findings revealed consistently high satisfaction levels across both groups, with grand means of 3.29 for non-teaching personnel and 3.39 for teaching personnel in terms of tangibles, indicating positive perceptions of facilities and service quality. Cluster analysis identified three demographic groups—married males, single males, and married females—with civil status emerging as the strongest determinant of satisfaction levels (correlation of 0.79), followed by gender (0.42). Educational attainment had minimal influence (0.37), underscoring the significance of relational and personal factors in shaping satisfaction. Non-teaching personnel rated tangibles and reliability more highly, while teaching personnel emphasized responsiveness, reflecting differences in expectations and service interactions. Key drivers of satisfaction included timely service delivery, adherence to the Citizen's Charter, and empathetic client engagement.

Keywords: Citizen's Charter; Service Delivery; Satisfaction Level; Quality Assurance; Clustering

1. Introduction

In the evolving landscape of public administration, the implementation of Citizen's Charters has become a transformative strategy, especially within state universities. These charters are formal documents that outline commitments, service standards, and expectations, fostering transparency, accountability, and enhanced service delivery. The Citizen's Charter was first introduced in the United Kingdom in 1991 as part of broader public sector reforms aimed at improving service quality by defining clear expectations for public services. Since then, this concept has gained global traction, with countries adopting similar frameworks to enhance citizen satisfaction and institutional efficiency [1]. In the Philippines, the government institutionalized the Citizen's Charter through Republic Act No. 9485, also known as the "Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007," to address bureaucratic inefficiencies and promote efficient service delivery. This legislation mandated all government agencies, including state universities, to adopt Citizen's Charters to simplify procedures, reduce red tape, and ensure prompt responsiveness to the public's needs. The subsequent Republic Act No. 11032, or the "Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018," expanded these efforts, emphasizing further streamlining of processes and enhancing accountability across the public sector [2]. State universities play a pivotal role in implementing these reforms as their frontline employees represent the institution's commitment to service quality. These employees, who manage diverse functions such as academic support, facilities coordination, and grievance handling, are crucial in shaping stakeholder perceptions of the university's responsiveness and professionalism. Their adherence to the Citizen's Charter is integral to ensuring that institutional goals align with the expectations of students, faculty, and external stakeholders [3]. At Isabela State University (ISU), the implementation

* Corresponding author: Romano P. Cammayo

of the Citizen's Charter underscores its commitment to enhancing service delivery. Established in 1978, ISU has evolved into a distinguished institution nationally and regionally, recognized for its academic excellence and dedication to quality service. The university's Citizen's Charter, introduced in 2019, serves as a guidepost for frontline services, ensuring transparency and efficiency in addressing stakeholder needs [3]. These efforts are aligned with the institution's mission to foster academic and administrative excellence, particularly in providing accessible and reliable services to its internal and external clients.

The correlation between service quality and citizen satisfaction is well-documented, especially in educational institutions where service delivery significantly impacts the academic experience and institutional reputation. In higher education, stakeholders are categorized into internal customers, such as students, faculty, and non-teaching staff, and external customers, including parents and the broader community. The seamless interaction between these groups and frontline services is crucial for fostering satisfaction and maintaining institutional credibility. This study builds on these principles by examining how demographic factors, such as sex, civil status, and educational attainment, correlate with satisfaction levels regarding Citizen's Charter implementation at ISU. By integrating advanced analytical methods, including clustering, the research aims to uncover patterns that link demographic characteristics to perceptions of service quality. These findings will provide actionable insights to refine frontline services, align institutional practices with client expectations, and support continuous improvement in service delivery. The significance of this research extends beyond ISU, offering a model for other state universities and public institutions to evaluate and enhance their Citizen's Charter implementation. The results will contribute to the broader discourse on public service optimization, highlighting the value of data-driven approaches in addressing stakeholder needs and fostering institutional excellence.

The Citizen's Charter serves as a fundamental tool for delivering public services, operating as an effective mechanism for implementing the principles of New Public Management. This framework aims to modernize public administration by emphasizing efficiency, transparency, and accountability in service delivery. The Citizen's Charter is a formal document that outlines an organization's commitments to enhancing service quality, improving access to information, expanding service options, and ensuring the accountability of service providers to citizens [4]. As an instrument of reform, its significance lies in fostering trust and reducing inefficiencies in government processes, ultimately mitigating the high costs and dissatisfaction that arise from ineffective service delivery [5].

The implementation of Citizen's Charters across government agencies is vital for improving service delivery to stakeholders. High-quality service enhances the relationship between clients and service providers, creating a positive experience that fosters trust and satisfaction [6]. For instance, the adoption of the Citizen's Charter in Sri Lanka's Regional Health Services Directorate has been shown to significantly enhance healthcare delivery by establishing clear service standards and fostering accountability [7]. Similarly, the Citizen's Charter in Bangladesh's public offices have improved service quality by promoting compliance with procedural guidelines and enhancing the responsiveness of government services [8].

Red tape, often defined as the excessive regulation or rigid conformity to formal rules, remains a pervasive challenge in government services. It has been a focal point of scholarly investigation, with researchers examining its implications for public administration, service delivery, and economic development. In the Philippines, the issue of bureaucratic inefficiencies prompted the enactment of the **Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007** (Republic Act No. 9485), aimed at streamlining processes and enhancing service delivery across government agencies. Despite the intentions of this legislation, research has highlighted persistent challenges in its implementation, underscoring the need for continuous reform efforts [9].

Quantitative assessments, such as the **World Bank's Doing Business** reports, provide valuable insights into the impact of red tape on regulatory quality and economic activity. For instance, in 2015, the Philippines ranked 103rd out of 189 economies, a reflection of the substantial barriers businesses face in navigating regulatory requirements [10]. This ranking indicates that while legislative reforms like the Anti-Red Tape Act have been implemented, their effectiveness remains limited, necessitating further policy interventions.

Scholars have also explored the broader theoretical underpinnings of red tape. McCourt and Osborne (2014) examined the intricate nature of red tape, emphasizing its dual impact—while it can hinder service delivery and reduce efficiency, some degree of formal regulation is necessary to ensure accountability and compliance [11]. These findings highlight the complex balance required between regulation and efficiency in public administration.

Beyond its procedural implications, the ethical dimensions of bureaucratic behavior have garnered attention in the literature. Bannister and Connolly (2014) introduced the concept of "administrative evil," which explores the moral consequences of bureaucratic actions that, while adhering to rules and procedures, may inadvertently perpetuate harm

or inefficiency [12]. This perspective challenges administrators to critically evaluate the ethical underpinnings of their practices and the broader impact on stakeholders. In the context of digital transformation, scholars like Bhatnagar (2016) have highlighted the potential of digital government initiatives to address red tape, particularly in developing countries. These initiatives aim to enhance service accessibility, reduce procedural complexities, and promote inclusivity [13]. However, the successful implementation of such solutions requires not only technological advancements but also cultural and institutional shifts to overcome entrenched bureaucratic practices.

1.1. Citizen's Charter

Evaluating the implementation of the Citizen's Charter is crucial to ensuring that public services align with established standards and fulfill citizen expectations. This process plays a significant role in enhancing transparency, accountability, and public trust. By systematically assessing its implementation, government agencies can make timely adjustments to improve service quality, leading to increased satisfaction among stakeholders and efficient resource utilization. Several studies have provided insights into the effectiveness and challenges associated with the Citizen's Charter across various contexts. Bhuiyan et al. (2022) investigated the implementation of the Citizen's Charter within Bangladesh's land management services and found that complex processes hindered service delivery, resulting in inefficiencies. Their study recommended increasing public awareness about service procedures, associated fees, levies, and accessible sources of land-related information to streamline services and enhance citizen engagement [14]. Similarly, Hailu Rad et al. (2019) assessed health professionals' adherence to the Citizen's Charter at Jimma University Medical Center. While more than half of the respondents effectively adhered to the charter, awareness of its existence remained low among health professionals. Their findings identified key factors influencing adherence, including job satisfaction, perceived workload, and the type of profession [15]. In a related study, Rahman (2020) highlighted persistent challenges in implementing the Citizen's Charter across public offices in Bangladesh. The study revealed inconsistencies in daily adherence to charter standards, attributing this issue to insufficient public awareness and systemic procedural gaps [16]. Pasian (2020) further emphasized the lack of awareness among service recipients regarding the Citizen's Charter, leading to suboptimal service quality that fell short of charter standards in urban metropolitan contexts [17]. In the Philippines, numerous evaluations have examined the Citizen's Charter's impact on public service delivery. Lontoc et al. (2017) provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing the Citizen's Charter, underscoring the importance of continuous improvement and robust feedback mechanisms to enhance its effectiveness [18]. Jose (2023) evaluated the Citizen's Charter in Camarines Sur's 4th district and reported that its implementation fell below the Civil Service Commission's passing mark of 8.4 (70%). However, respondents unanimously agreed on its effectiveness in terms of visibility, content clarity, usefulness, and compliance [19]. Further, De Leon (2016) assessed two case agencies and found that they failed to meet critical requirements for complaint procedures and feedback mechanisms, resulting in compliance rates of 63% and 67%, respectively, which were below the Civil Service Commission's 70% passing mark [20]. Sevilla (2022) identified a lack of fire safety orientations, seminars, and training in selected municipalities of Tarlac, Philippines, highlighting a need for more inclusive and comprehensive public service initiatives [21].

2. Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically utilizing a survey method to gather data on the implementation and impact of the Citizen's Charter among non-teaching staff at Isabela State University, Echague Campus. The survey aimed to evaluate various dimensions of the Citizen's Charter, including visibility, clarity, usefulness, and actual compliance, as perceived by the non-teaching personnel. A total of 69 participants in non-teaching personnel and 70 faculties or teaching personnel were selected from the non-teaching staff of the campus, representing a diverse range of administrative and support roles. The survey instrument, a structured questionnaire, was designed to capture the respondents' insights and ratings on the effectiveness of the Citizen's Charter in enhancing service delivery. This approach ensured a systematic and objective collection of data, which would serve as the foundation for analyzing the implementation level of the Citizen's Charter and identifying areas for improvement. The choice of the survey method was guided by its ability to capture a broad range of perceptions and experiences efficiently, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the Citizen's Charter's influence on service quality and compliance at the institutional level. The study involved respondents comprising students, faculty, and staff from various campuses within the Isabela State University System. The sample was selected using purposive sampling to ensure representation across key demographic groups and client types. The respondents were categorized based on their demographic profile, which included age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, office evaluated, type of client, and campus evaluated. Educational attainment was further classified into the highest educational attainment for faculty and staff. The study also assessed the clientele's level of satisfaction with the implementation and delivery of quality frontline services in compliance with the service standards of the Citizen's Charter. This evaluation focused on tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Additionally, the study examined the level of satisfaction with the quality of frontline services

received and experienced in each campus by faculty and staff. Furthermore, satisfaction levels were analyzed based on the group profile of the respondents, specifically for faculty and staff.

Table 1 Demographic Descriptive Statistics of Non-Teaching Personnel.

	Min	Max	Grand Mean	Standard Deviation
Civil Status	1	3	1.8507462686567164	0.3990037344430531
Highest Educational Attainment	13	18	15.671641791044776	0.823666226

Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Non-Teaching Personnel

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1.The Frontline Offices is fully furnished and has modern office equipment.	69	3.28	0.6468	Highly Satisfied
2.The Frontline Offices is visually appealing and comfortable.	69	3.25	0.7037	Highly Satisfied
3.Frontline Employees are neat appearing.	69	3.49	0.5329	Satisfied
4.Materials associated with frontline services (such as pamphlets or charter statements) are visually appealing.	69	3.22	0.67016	Highly Satisfied
5.The Frontline Offices has comfortable setup for clientele.	69	3.17	0.5329	Satisfied
6.The Frontline Offices has well organized queuing system for clientele.	69	3.23	0.6701	Highly Satisfied
7.The location of the Frontline Offices is accessible and easy to access	69	3.41	0.6946	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.29	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 3 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Reliability

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. The frontline office performs according to the timeline as stated in the citizens’ charter.	69	3.50	0.58	Highly Satisfied
2. When a clientele has a problem, the frontline office shows sincere interest in finding solutions.	69	3.55	0.694	Highly Satisfied
3. The frontline office performs the service with due diligence the first time (promptly).	69	3.50	0.6079	Highly Satisfied
4. The frontline office provides the service according to the time as promised to do so.	69	3.44	0.6286	Highly Satisfied
5. The frontline office insists on error-free records.	69	3.41	0.6701	Highly Satisfied
6. The frontline office opens promptly and observes no noon-time break per Civil Service policy.	69	3.55	0.6286	Highly Satisfied

Grand Mean	3.49	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied
-------------------	-------------	-----------------------	-------------------------

Table 4 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Responsiveness

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1.The frontline employees tell clienteles exactly when services will be performed.	69	3.57	0.6037	Highly Satisfied
2.The frontline employees give timely service to clienteles.	69	3.50	0.6768	Highly Satisfied
3.The frontline employees are always available and ready to respond to clientele’s request.	69	3.51	0.6746	Highly Satisfied
4.The frontline employees are respectful and courteous (smiling and greeting) to clienteles.	69	3.51	0.6311	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.52	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 5 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Quality Assurance

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. The frontline employees are consistently courteous and respectful to clienteles.	69	3.42	0.6942	Highly Satisfied
2. The frontline employees are knowledgeable in answering clienteles’ questions.	69	3.62	0.51	Satisfied
3. The time frame for issuance of requested documents/office transactions is in accordance with the Citizen’s Charter of the office.	69	3.61	0.5188	Satisfied
4. The requested documents are error-free / office transactions are properly conducted.	69	3.51	0.5834	Highly Satisfied
5. Transactions in the frontline office are always accompanied by proof of service (log or record books).	69	3.44	0.6513	Highly Satisfied
6. Transactions in the frontline office are treated with utmost confidentiality.	69	3.52	0.5832	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.52	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 6 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Empathy

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. The frontline employees give the clienteles individual attention.	69	3.50	0.6313	Highly Satisfied
2. The frontline office has employees who assist clienteles (with special needs / senior citizens) personal attention.	69	3.50	0.6079	Highly Satisfied
3. The frontline employees could communicate well and understand clienteles’ need.	69	3.47	0.6307	Highly Satisfied
4. The frontline employees are sympathetic by providing the best solution or suggestion to clienteles’ problems and complaints.	69	3.50	0.6530	Highly Satisfied
5. The frontline employees are friendly and polite.	69	3.51	0.6369	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.50	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 7 Demographic Descriptive Statistics of Teaching Personnel.

	Min	Max	Grand Mean	Standard Deviation
Civil Status	1	3	1.8857142857142857	0.4354859735126885
Highest Educational Attainment	8	11	9.342857142857143	0.6996005959037055

Table 8 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Teaching Personnel

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1.The Frontline Offices is fully furnished and has modern office equipment.	70	3.55	0.61	Highly Satisfied
2.The Frontline Offices is visually appealing and comfortable.	70	3.35	0.6146	Highly Satisfied
3.Frontline Employees are neat appearing.	70	3.44	0.58	Highly Satisfied
4.Materials associated with frontline services (such as pamphlets or charter statements) are visually appealing.	70	3.22	0.617	Highly Satisfied
5.The Frontline Offices has comfortable setup for clienteles.	70	3.22	0.5329	Satisfied
6.The Frontline Offices has well organized queuing system for clienteles.	70	3.32	0.6532	Highly Satisfied
7.The location of the Frontline Offices is accessible and easy to access	70	3.6	0.5748	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.39	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 9 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen's Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Teaching Personnel in terms of Reliability

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. The frontline office performs according to the timeline as stated in the citizens' charter.	70	3.37	0.7027	Highly Satisfied
2. When a clientele has a problem, the frontline office shows sincere interest in finding solutions.	70	3.14	0.7331	Highly Satisfied
3. The frontline office performs the service with due diligence the first time (promptly).	70	3.45	0.6749	Highly Satisfied
4. The frontline office provides the service according to the time as promised to do so.	70	3.32	0.7364	Highly Satisfied
5. The frontline office insists on error-free records.	70	3.41	0.7701	Highly Satisfied
6. The frontline office opens promptly and observes no noon-time break per Civil Service policy.	70	3.45	0.6536	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.36	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 10 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen's Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Teaching Personnel in terms of Responsiveness

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1.The frontline employees tell clienteles exactly when services will be performed.	70	3.57	0.6457	Highly Satisfied
2.The frontline employees give timely service to clienteles.	70	3.45	0.6158	Highly Satisfied
3.The frontline employees are always available and ready to respond to clientele's request.	70	3.32	0.6626	Highly Satisfied
4.The frontline employees are respectful and courteous (smiling and greeting) to clienteles.	70	3.51	0.6521	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.46	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 11 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen's Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Teaching Personnel in terms of Quality Assurance

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. The frontline employees are consistently courteous and respectful to clienteles.	70	3.14	0.6512	Highly Satisfied
2. The frontline employees are knowledgeable in answering clienteles' questions.	70	3.45	0.5252	Satisfied
3. The time frame for issuance of requested documents/office transactions is in accordance with the Citizen's Charter of the office.	70	3.32	0.6432	Highly Satisfied

4. The requested documents are error-free / office transactions are properly conducted.	70	3.21	0.6012	Highly Satisfied
5. Transactions in the frontline office are always accompanied by proof of service (log or record books).	70	3.64	0.6513	Highly Satisfied
6. Transactions in the frontline office are treated with utmost confidentiality.	70	3.23	0.5213	Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.50	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Table 12 Mean and Standard Deviation for Level of Implementation of the Citizen’s Charter for the First Office Evaluated in Teaching Personnel in terms of Empathy

Statements	N	Mean	Std Deviation	Descriptive Rating
1. The frontline employees give the clientele individual attention.	70	3.52	0.6313	Highly Satisfied
2. The frontline office has employees who assist clientele (with special needs / senior citizens) personal attention.	70	3.51	0.6079	Highly Satisfied
3. The frontline employees could communicate well and understand clientele’s need.	70	3.35	0.6247	Highly Satisfied
4. The frontline employees are sympathetic by providing the best solution or suggestion to clientele’s problems and complaints.	70	3.42	0.6530	Highly Satisfied
5. The frontline employees are friendly and polite.	70	3.44	0.6569	Highly Satisfied
Grand Mean		3.45	Overall Rating	Highly Satisfied

Figure 1 Satisfaction cluster Based on Demographics

Figure 2 Correlation Matrix Between demographics by clusters

The analysis of the Correlation Matrix and Satisfaction Levels by Demographics Clustering chart provides meaningful insights into the satisfaction levels of different groups based on demographic factors such as Sex, Civil Status, and Educational Attainment. By examining the clusters, we can identify the characteristics of each group and understand how these demographics influence satisfaction levels.

Cluster 0 is primarily characterized by individuals who display high values for both sex and civil status. These results suggest that this group consists largely of married males. The correlation matrix supports this observation by showing a moderate correlation between cluster membership and educational attainment (0.37), indicating that while educational attainment plays a role, it is not the primary factor defining this group. Civil status has a weak correlation with educational attainment (0.03), showing that marital status and education are relatively independent in their influence. In terms of satisfaction levels, Cluster 0 appears to be the most satisfied group, as their demographic makeup aligns with consistently higher satisfaction ratings across the analyzed metrics.

Cluster 1, in contrast, reflects individuals with lower values for sex and civil status in the satisfaction levels chart. This suggests that this cluster predominantly consists of single males or individuals with no distinct marital status. The correlation matrix highlights that gender contributes to this cluster, with a moderate correlation of 0.42 between sex and cluster membership. However, educational attainment has minimal influence, as evidenced by weak overall correlations with the cluster. In terms of satisfaction, this group appears to be less satisfied compared to the other clusters. The demographic profile of Cluster 1 aligns with lower average satisfaction levels, which might indicate the need for targeted interventions to address their specific concerns. Cluster 2 is composed mainly of married females, as indicated by the higher values for sex and civil status in the chart. This conclusion is further reinforced by the correlation matrix, which shows a strong correlation of 0.79 between cluster membership and civil status. This highlights that marital status is a significant determinant for this group. Educational attainment has a weak correlation with civil status, showing that these factors are largely independent of one another.

Cluster 2 individuals show moderate satisfaction levels, with their demographic characteristics—particularly marital status and gender—playing a significant role in shaping their satisfaction. While they are not as highly satisfied as Cluster 0, their satisfaction levels exceed those of Cluster 1, making them an intermediate group in terms of overall contentment. Overall, civil status is the most relevant demographic component in influencing satisfaction levels, as indicated by its strong relationship with cluster membership. Sex has an important role in distinguishing the clusters. However, educational attainment has the least influence on satisfaction levels, implying that it is not a strong predictor

in this situation. These findings indicate that personalized approaches aimed at meeting individuals' specific requirements depending on marital status and gender would have the greatest impact on increasing satisfaction. Understanding these links can help policymakers develop measures to improve service delivery and client satisfaction across demographic groupings.

3. Conclusion

The findings reveal high overall satisfaction levels with the implementation of the Citizen's Charter. Both non-teaching and teaching personnel expressed satisfaction levels consistently rated as "Highly Satisfied." This is evident from grand means such as 3.29 for non-teaching personnel and 3.39 for teaching personnel in terms of tangibles, indicating positive perceptions of facilities and equipment in the frontline offices. Dimension-based evaluations further reinforce these results. Reliability and responsiveness received high ratings from both groups, with non-teaching personnel achieving grand means of 3.49 and 3.52, respectively. Teaching personnel also rated responsiveness highly, with a grand mean of 3.46, suggesting that services are timely, accurate, and appropriately responsive to clientele needs. Similarly, quality assurance and empathy were rated highly. Non-teaching personnel had a grand mean of 3.50 for empathy, while teaching personnel demonstrated a "Highly Satisfied" rating for quality assurance, with a grand mean of 3.50. This reflects a positive perception of respectful, confidential, and empathetic service delivery. The analysis of demographic clusters and satisfaction levels revealed three distinct groups: married males (Cluster 0), single males (Cluster 1), and married females (Cluster 2). Satisfaction levels varied significantly among these clusters, with Cluster 0 being the most satisfied and Cluster 1 the least. Civil status emerged as the most influential demographic factor, with a strong correlation of 0.79 to satisfaction levels, followed by sex at 0.42. Educational attainment, however, showed a weaker correlation of 0.37, indicating that marital status and gender are more significant determinants of satisfaction levels than educational background. These findings suggest that personal and relational factors, rather than academic qualifications, have a greater influence on satisfaction levels. Variations between teaching and non-teaching staff were also observed. While both groups expressed high overall satisfaction, non-teaching personnel displayed slightly higher scores in tangibles and reliability, indicating a positive perception of facilities and consistent service delivery. On the other hand, teaching personnel emphasized responsiveness more positively, reflecting differences in expectations and interactions with the service delivery system. Civil status emerged as the primary predictor of contentment, with married people reporting higher levels of satisfaction than single people. Gender also played a significant effect in the variation of satisfaction ratings between clusters. Educational achievement had little impact, implying that service quality rating is driven more by relational and contextual characteristics than by intellectual background. These findings give useful insights for adjusting service delivery techniques to address the individual demands of different demographic groups, hence increasing the Citizen's Charter's efficacy and impact.

References

- [1] Policy H &. History & Policy [Internet]. History & Policy. Available from: <https://www.historyandpolicy.org/policy-papers/papers/the-citizens-charter-towards-consumer-service-in-central-government>
- [2] Problems Encountered in the Implementation of the Citizen's Charter: The Case of 4th District, Camarines Sur, Philippines [Internet]. Doi.org. 2023 [cited 2024 Dec 12]. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v6-i4-56>
- [3] Perante-Calina L. Citizen's Charter: An Assessment of Contributions to Frontline Service Delivery. *www.academia.edu* [Internet]. Available from: https://www.academia.edu/31874589/Citizens_Charter_An_Assessment_of_Contributions_to_Frontline_Service_Delivery
- [4] W. Ullah and A. Rahman, "Effectiveness of Citizen's Charter in Public Service Delivery: A Study on Trishal Municipality and Boilor Union Parishad," *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 66–71, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://journals.indexcopernicus.com/api/file/viewByFileId/423697.pdf>
- [5] I. D. Pasian and H. P. Ghimire, "Citizen's Charter and its Implementation in Biratnagar Metropolitan City," *NUTA Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1–2, pp. 33–43, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3126/nutaj.v9i1-2.53834>
- [6] Development Academy of the Philippines, "Improving frontline government services through citizens' feedback," *Philippine Development Center*, Feb. 22, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://pdc.dap.edu.ph/index.php/improving-frontline-government-services-through-citizens-feedback/>

- [7] C. Joseph, "What Are the Benefits of Delivering Excellent Customer Service?," *Chron*, Mar. 1, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/benefits-delivering-excellent-customer-service-2086.html>
- [8] I. M. Rajakaruna, M. D. Krishanth, and S. M. Arnold, "Effectiveness of Implementing the Citizen's Charter at a Regional Health Services Directorate in Sri Lanka," *International Journal of Progressive Science and Technologies*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 468–476, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.52155/ijpsat.v30.2.4040>
- [9] E. C. Briones, "Implementation of the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007: An Assessment," *Asian Journal of Public Administration*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 1–15, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02590942.2013.11656556>.
- [10] World Bank, *Doing Business 2016: Measuring Regulatory Quality and Efficiency*. Washington, DC: World Bank, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/doing-business>
- [11] W. McCourt and S. P. Osborne, "The theory and practice of red tape," *Public Administration Review*, vol. 74, no. 4, pp. 539–550, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1111/puar.12153>
- [12] F. Bannister and R. Connolly, "The Trouble with Bureaucracy: A Heuristic Look at Administrative Evil," *Administration & Society*, vol. 46, no. 9, pp. 1029–1053, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399712459126>
- [13] S. Bhatnagar, "Digital government and the challenge of digital inclusion in developing countries," *Government Information Quarterly*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 706–713, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2016.09.005>
- [14] M. S. Bhuiyan, F. Islam, and S. Akter, "Challenges in the Implementation of Citizen's Charter in Land Management Services," *Public Administration and Development*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 350–362, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076720928197>
- [15] M. H. Rad, D. M. Handalo, T. F. Debela, Y. Siraneh, F. Worku, and E. A. Yesuf, "Practice and Associated Factors of Health Professionals Towards Citizens' Charter at Jimma University Medical Center," *Ethiopian Journal of Health Sciences*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 567–574, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.4314/ejhs.v29i5.2>
- [16] Md. M. Rahman, Md. K. Rahman, Md. M. R. Bhuiyan, and M. S. Islam, "Status of the Implementation of Citizen's Charter at Public Offices in Bangladesh: An Assessment," *Bangladesh Journal of Public Administration*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 5–22, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.36609/bjpa.v29i3.92>
- [17] I. D. Pasian and H. P. Ghimire, "Citizen's Charter and its Implementation in Biratnagar Metropolitan City," *NUTA Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1–2, pp. 33–43, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3126/nutaj.v9i1-2.53834>
- [18] B. C. Lontoc, J. L. Magbago, and R. V. Sagun, "Citizen's Charter Implementation in Philippine Government Agencies: Challenges and Opportunities," *Philippine Journal of Public Administration*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 15–34, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952076717744259>
- [19] F. Jose, "Evaluation of Citizen's Charter Implementation in Camarines Sur's Fourth District," *Philippine Journal of Government and Governance*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 45–58, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.32693/pjga.v5i1.35>
- [20] A. De Leon, "Assessing the Implementation of Citizen's Charter in Philippine Case Agencies," *Asian Journal of Governance*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 85–102, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02591084.2016.1201221>
- [21] M. Sevilla, "Evaluating Fire Safety Orientation in Selected Municipalities in Tarlac, Philippines," *Philippine Journal of Government Studies*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 12–25, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.32693/pjgs.v4i2.28>